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1. General Progress of the action

1.1 Please indicate the progress of the action during the period covered by this report:

- The action has fully achieved its objectives for the period.
- The action has achieved most of its objectives for the period with relatively minor deviations.
- The action has achieved some of its objectives but corrective action is required.
- The action has failed to achieve critical objectives and/or is severely delayed.

1.2 Please describe the general scientific progress of the action during the period covered by this report (including by giving qualitative indicators and by describing deliverables and milestones achieved):

1.2.1 Progress in WP2 “Development of Modelling Framework”

The secondments performed by the different Papila partners during the first year of the project allowed significant progress in WP2 regarding the development of the Papila modelling framework. A coordinated model study led by FMI (Finland) was conceived during a web conference organized in July 2018 with participation from the modeling teams involved in the project. A specific splinter meeting was also organized during the IGAC conference in Takamatsu/Japan, where a detailed protocol for the coordinated modeling study was drafted by FMI (Finland) in collaboration with different modeling teams from both Europe and South America. This modeling protocol document is made available for the project partners on the Papila website (<http://papila-h2020.eu>). We present in the following sections a summary of work progress in WP2 of achieved by several individual partners.

FMI (Finland): FMI is leading the activities concerning the development of the modeling framework in WP2. A first modeling study for January and July 2015 is organized with the Papila modeling teams and a detailed protocol was drafted and communicated to all partners. First results of the modeling study will be discussed during the technical workshop that will be organized after the first Papila summer school in Santiago, Chile in November of this year. FMI has already an operational air pollution forecasting system providing daily forecasts of major pollutants (Particulates, O₃, NO_x, CO, SO₂) for Europe and Asia as well as for South America through their global scale forecasting system. High resolution simulations dedicated for South America are being prepared as part of the modeling study and activities within WP2.

INERIS (France): INERIS is involved in WP2 providing expertise to the development of tools permitting the assessment, and possibly monetization, of ozone damage on crops and air pollutant impacts on health. This work is shared with UCL (Chile), hosting a post-doctoral researcher who spends one year of secondment at INERIS. The first part of activity of the postdoc researcher has focused on a bibliographical study on the availability of concentration-response functions for Chile and South America and on the identification of local databases

(population and health & agriculture). Both actions are ongoing. As a second major activity the adaptation of the tool developed by INERIS to study the agricultural impact of air pollution has started. Furthermore, the data and development needs for the creation of the health impact assessment tool have been assessed. Regarding the data, various databases have been found that are relevant for the health tool (mortality, hospital admissions & discharges..., population) while data availability is less obvious for agriculture (global FAO data are available but there is a lack of local crop studies giving information on phenology, ozone accumulation period and particularly on concentration-response functions specific to the region). Further investigation is ongoing to select the target species that may be addressed in this work.

MET Norway: In 2018 MET Norway set up its Air Quality model (EMEP) for calculations of air concentrations in the LAC domain (Latin America and Caribbean). This included the generation of meteorological data by running the ECMWF-IFS model, collection of appropriate emission data, as well as initial conditions and chemical boundary conditions. The EMEP model was successfully run for different seasons of 2015 and compared to available measurements. An experienced researcher from MET Norway was seconded to the University of Chile to get started with the EMEP modelling efforts for South America, installing the EMEP model on a High Performance Computing system in Chile, and to make Chilean researchers acquainted with the model code and setup. In addition, the downscaling method 'uEMEP' was tested for the agglomeration of Santiago, using proxy data on road traffic emissions. A secondment report was submitted, providing more details on the model calculations and their evaluation.

MPI-M (Germany): Following the protocol of the modeling study defined with other modeling teams, MPI-M started setting up the WRF-Chem model over South America using both the model version v3.6.1 already installed at MPI-M computing systems as well as the latest recently released version v4.0. Preliminary simulations are being performed focusing on dust outbreaks in Argentina. In parallel, model input datasets are prepared in order to run the model with full chemistry. Some technical issues due to e.g. compilers, memory scaling and computing capacity were encountered by the postdoctoral researcher who was seconded to MPI-M from CNEA (Argentina) but progress is made in resolving such issues and the first model simulations dedicated for the modeling study are expected to be started soon.

UMSA (Bolivia): The WRF model is been run in UMSA in two versions (v3.7 and 4.0) both with nested domains. Training activities were performed for getting acquainted specially with the last WRF version. Version 3.7 was used to generate wind fields for a specific region (Alpacoma) near La Paz due to an important landfill rupture. With the latest WRF version, the model has been tested in two ways: checking for topography and evaluating the diurnal cycle of winds. The model outputs will be used as inputs of the chemistry transport model (CHIMERE). A secondment to CNRS is planned in May-June of this year in order to setup and run CHIMERE at UMSA.

USP (Brazil): Great progress has been made at USP with air quality modeling using WRF-Chem model. With the combination of experimental data obtained from a thematic project NUANCE (Narrowing the Uncertainties on Aerosol and Climate Change in Sao Paulo State), the main properties of atmospheric aerosol particles over the Metropolitan Area of Sao

Paulo (MASP), in southeastern Brazil, were studied. Impacts of the different fuels used in MASP (bio-diesel, gasoil and ethanol) were considered to the reactivity in the atmosphere (Vara-Vela et al., 2018). The diesel used in MASP contains 8% of biodiesel and the passengers cars can run with ethanol, gasohol (gasoline with 25% ethanol) and any amount of both in the case of the flex-fuels vehicles. The fleet in MASP is of more than 7 million cars. But not less important is the emission by biomass burning, charcoal and wood burning in restaurant and waste burning. The combined application of aerosol data and WRF-Chem simulations made it possible to represent some of the most important aerosol properties such as size distribution and cloud condensation nuclei (CCN) activation, besides allowing us to evaluate the contributions of anthropogenic and biomass burning sources to the PM_{2.5} loadings in the MASP. The results indicate the potential importance of biomass burning sources for air quality in the MASP, and underscore the need for more accurate representations of aerosol emissions to reduce uncertainties in the model predictions. There are great uncertainties in representing the vehicular and other combustion sources in the emission module of the model. Other important results are being obtained trying to describe in better way the boundary layer process improving the local climate zone classification in MASP (Pellegatti Franco et al., 2019). New boundary conditions are also being used with the use of the global MOZART predictions in the WRF-Chem modeling for the MASP (Gavidia-Calderon et al., 2018).

UNAM (Mexico): An air quality forecasting system is currently operational for central México at UNAM. Model predictions for the periods defined in the Papila modeling protocol have been prepared and are ready for comparison with other model results. In addition to country wide air quality emissions with 9x9 km resolution a set of 5 regions in Mexico were selected to develop a high-resolution emissions inventory (3x3 km). A Mexico wide gridded information for crop areas as well as a wide information on population in a grid have also been prepared for exposure evaluation.

CNEA (Argentina): CNEA has conducted WRF-Chem model simulations for dust and with full chemistry to investigate the contribution of different aerosols to air pollution in Argentina. A postdoctoral researcher from CNEA was seconded to MPI-M and another researcher is expected to be seconded soon in order to work on different modelling aspects of WP2. The seconded researcher to MPI-M has updated the WRF-Chem version used in MPI-M and is currently preparing the model simulations for the specific modeling study organised by FMI (Finland).

UCL (Chile): The CHIMERE model has been implemented for Chile at the University of Chile (UCL) in close collaboration with the team from the Laboratoire de Météorologie Dynamique (LMD) from CNRS, responsible for the development and maintenance of the regional CHIMERE model. The new national emission inventory for Chile developed within WP3 (see Section 1.2.2) is now used to apply the WRF-CHIMERE modeling system to Chile. Initially, the modeling system was only applied to simulate the atmospheric dispersion of urban pollutants in the metropolitan region. This new inventory allows extending the use of the model to the entire country. As a first test, the modeling system has been applied to simulate the dispersion of urban pollutants in Chile during a winter month to explore its performance to simulate air quality linked to residential emissions (Figure 1). Also, the EMEP model is being run fed with HTAP and local emissions and using both ECMWF and WRF meteorological data. This system has been applied to explore the behavior of particles and ozone in winter and summer months. This work has been carried out in close collaboration with MET Norway.

Figure 1: Hourly surface concentrations of PM_{2.5} at 21:00 (LT) on June 16th 2016

1.2.2 Progress in WP3 “Surface Emissions”

The CNRS team at Laboratoire d’Aerologie (France) is leading the activities on surface emissions within WP3. In addition to CNRS, several other partners have been working on improving surface emissions in different regions of Latin America. The progress made in different tasks of this WP by CNRS as well as by some individual partners is described in the following sections.

Task 3.1: Definition of a preliminary surface emissions dataset to be used in the first year of Papila

CNRS has worked on the definition of a preliminary surface emissions dataset that can be used by the Papila modelling teams. The CNRS group is also coordinating the project on emissions in the Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service (CAMS). As part of CAMS, a global inventory providing emissions at a 0.1x0.1 degree resolution has been developed. This inventory, called CAMS-GLOB-ANT covers the 2000-2019 period, and provides emissions for several sectors. An example of the emissions given by the CAMS-GLOB-ANT dataset is shown in Figure 2 for the nitrogen oxides. These emissions can be accessed by the PAPILA partners through the ECCAD emissions database (<https://eccad.aeris-data.fr/>).

Task 3.2: Evaluation of all publicly available data concerning anthropogenic emissions in Latin America

Datasets from several inventories providing emissions at the global scale for atmospheric compounds have been gathered. Comparisons of the emissions provided by these inventories for CO, NO_x, SO₂, NMVOCs, Ammonia and for particles are being analysed. The focus of the analysis is the 1980-2019 period. A peer-reviewed paper is under preparation and will be submitted in 2019.

Figure 2: 2019 NO_x emissions from the CAMS-GLOB-ANT inventory, which can be used as a preliminary PAPILA inventory for Latin America

Task 3.3: Definition of a Latin America regional inventory

During a secondment in Spring of 2018, CNRS worked with the group at UCL to develop and evaluate a gridded inventory of emissions for Chile. During another secondment from October 2018 to January 2019, a colleague from CNES worked at CNRS on the development of an inventory of anthropogenic emissions for Argentina. This work will continue during the coming months. The datasets developed as part of these secondments are available through the ECCAD database but since they are not yet finalized, the data have for now a restricted access. More work on these developments are planned during the upcoming 5-months secondments to CNRS of two scientists, one from Chile and one from Colombia.

CNEA (Argentina): CNEA has significantly contributed to the WP3 activities on surface emissions particularly to the above mentioned tasks performed at CNRS during the secondment of a researcher from CNEA. A preliminary analysis of different datasets providing anthropogenic emissions or ancillary data in Latin America was conducted during this secondment. Available datasets for Chile, Argentina and Colombia have been compared with the emissions inventory developed at CNRS within the CAMS project. Ongoing analysis is focusing on other chemical species (VOCs) and specific sectors (transportation, fuel combustion, etc.).

UCL (Chile): A national emission inventory for Chile has been developed in collaboration with the Laboratoire d'Aérodologie (LA) from CNRS. Initially, only a gridded emission inventory was available for the Metropolitan Region in Central Chile. During most of 2018, a national gridded emission inventory for Chile was developed based on the estimates available at the Registry of Transfer and Emission of Pollutants (<http://www.retc.cl>) from the Ministry of the Environment. The emissions at this registry are available at a communal level and were distributed onto a 1x1 km gridded map by using different databases such as population density, road maps and land use.

UNAL (Colombia): The objective of UNAL in WP3 is assessing and improving emissions inventories at the national level in Colombia, and using them to upgrade global emissions inventories. In order to achieve this objective, national greenhouse gas emissions (3rd National Communication), disaggregated at the department (state) level have been received from the Ministry of the Environment and Sustainable Development. First estimates of the national criteria pollutant emissions, including PM, SO₂, NO_x and CO have also been performed. The emissions datasets for some available species (e.g. CO, NO_x and SO₂) from the local inventory have been compared with data from the CAMS emissions inventory developed by CNRS. Discussions with partners in Argentina and Chile have also been conducted in order to coordinate the following actions within WP3:

- Consolidation and disaggregation of transport emissions inventories
- Estimation and disaggregation of national ammonia emissions inventories
- Estimation and disaggregation of national volatile organic compounds emissions inventories

These activities are in their initial phase and will be further developed as part of future secondments from UNAL to CNRS and Chile.

UMSA (Bolivia): UMSA started working on the development of improved surface emissions for Bolivia and Latin America during a secondment to UGA in France. Analysis was conducted for available gaseous mercury measured at Chacaltaya mountain between July 2014 and February 2016, including validation of data, general statistics, possible sources and sinks (through a back-trajectory analysis) and possible influence of ENSO events. As a result, a first draft based on these two topics is being elaborated and shared with other partners and potentially will be submitted for publication.

1.2.3 Progress in WP4 “Space Observations in Support of Air Pollution Forecasts”

KNMI (The Netherlands) is leading the WP4 activities concerning space observations. The primary aim has been to evaluate new sources of air pollution detectable by TROPOMI as compared to prior satellite mission owing to greatly improved spatial resolution and noise. For example, seasonally averaged maps of TROPOMI NO₂ have been generated with a 2 x 2 km resolution. These maps indicate that South American sources are relatively small as compare to other persistent global hotspots including Benelux, China, South African Highveld regions. Much smaller sources of NO₂, SO₂, CO, absorbing aerosol are now detectable with TROPOMI. The spatial footprint of cities is detectable including: Rio de Janeiro, Sao Paulo, Buenos Aires, Santiago, and Lima. Regions affected by biomass burning and volcanic activity are also clearly visible. KNMI has been in contact with UNAL (Colombia) who started comparing TROPOMI data with model results in order to further work on project aspects related to satellite observations during the upcoming scheduled exchanges. KNMI expects also to send a satellite-emission inversion specialist to the combined GEIA meeting / PAPILA summer school in Santiago, Chile in fall 2019 (see section 1.2.5 on WP6 progress).

1.2.4 Progress in WP5 “Ground-based Observations and Model Evaluation”

UGA (France): Like most cities in the Latin America and the Caribbean (LAC) region, La Paz / El Alto agglomeration has concentrations of particulate matter above the WHO guidelines with consequences for both health and the environment, in particular with a urban population of more than two millions exposed to particulate matter. The atmospheric environment in La Paz/El Alto is also deteriorating due to rainforest degradation in the low- and mid-altitude surrounding lands, associated to intense biomass burning episodes that are affecting the whole area during specific periods of the year. The environmental challenges facing La Paz-El Alto are on the one side very typical of other Latin American cities (multiple stressors to Air Quality at local scale and at the larger regional Amazonian Basin scale) and specific due to the very high altitude of the urban area (between 3400m and 4100 m asl), the complex orography, and the low-income conditions of its inhabitants.

In PAPILA, UGA is leading activities on WP5 and has contributed to Tasks 5.1 and 5.2 during the first year of the project:

Task 5.1: Compilation of existing ground based observations

This task is done within a GAW initiative. UGA and UPR-PR organized a meeting to form the basis of a peer-reviewed paper to report the following: a description of the network and status of data provision in 2017, current observed properties at the different sites, and main observations from the past decade, including the LAC region. The scientific content of the paper will come from reviewing previous studies on variability/trends/model-measurement intercomparisons, and extending these with new years. The paper should serve as a benchmark paper describing the quality assurance and quality control procedures for the data, resulting well documented, harmonised and comparable data on regional scales.

Task 5.2: Development of a common database for observations

Model evaluation requires the availability of high quality observations. In Task 5.2, UGA is contributing to developing a specific database for evaluating the Air Quality in the city of LaPaz. A large measurement campaign was organized in La Paz from December 2017 to June 2018 that will complete information available for modelling purposes. It is the most extensive

instrumental deployment performed in LAC since MILAGRO experiments in Mexico City, clearly unique in the Tropical Andes.

TROPOS (Germany): Activities have been conducted in TROPOS on population exposure models and health indices. As part of the intensive measurement campaign done in La Paz, Bolivia was designed to isolate the impact of transportation options (i.e. cable car, microbus, and walking) on ultrafine particle deposition dose. Two mobile devices (Aethalometer, MA200) were used to measure the black carbon (BC) concentration in two major cities in Bolivia. The instruments used in this study were carried in backpacks by the researchers and volunteers. The mobile measurement was conducted along five (5) different streets in La Paz and El Alto city. The result of the measurement campaign will give the local spatial distribution and exposure concentration to BC concentration in the streets of La Paz and El Alto. Furthermore, an estimation of the potential dose inhaled by a commuter in different transportation alternatives during a trip will also be determined. A scientific publication on the estimation of potential deposition dose is currently in progress.

A smaller part of the mobile measurement is a feasibility study on the new method to directly measure the dose of deposited black carbon mass in the respiratory tract. A scientific paper was successfully published recently (Madueño et al., 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2019.02.021>). The mobile measurement was able to obtain aerosol particle mass concentrations at wavelengths 880 nm (interpreted as black carbon), 375 nm (can be interpreted as ultraviolet particulate matter-wood smoke, tobacco, and/or biomass burning), 625 nm, 528 nm, and 470 nm (fit for source apportionment investigation).

UMSA (Bolivia) and TROPOS (Germany): In order to quantify the ambient concentration of pollutants and produce real data to feed air quality models within Papila, two air quality stations were setup in La Paz metropolis from January to May 2018. The idea is to evaluate how much pollutants are produced in anthropogenic activities (mobile and stationary sources as examples), so two urban background areas were chosen: one station in La Paz city in the top of a children’s museum, and the other station in El Alto city in the middle of the international airport. The parameters measured in each station are summed up in table 1. In both stations particles with diameters smaller than 10 micrometers were measured. The campaign was successfully carried out and there is more than 90 percent of useful data. Currently, the information produced in the campaign is still being analysed. Subsequently, these results will be used as input to evaluate the selected air quality model.

Table 1: Pollutants components measured in each station

El Alto		La Paz
Particle aerosols	Reactive gases	Particle aerosols
Particle number size distribution From 3nm to 20um	Ozone	Particle number size distribution From 10nm to 20um
Particle mass concentration Target spices	Carbon monoxide	Absorption coefficient Passive sampling
Scattering coefficient Absorption coefficient Aerosol optical depth Passive sampling		

1.2.5 Progress in WP6 “Transfer of Knowledge, Education and Capacity Building”

Together with UCL (Chile) and CNRS (France), MPI-M (Germany) will organize the first Papila summer school that will take place in Chile in November 2019. A first teleconference with partners from both Europe and South America was organised to discuss the potential programme, topics and dates of the summer school. Details of the local arrangements (location, lodging, timeline) as well as of financial aspects were discussed with UCL during the visit of the project leader (Dr. Guy Brasseur) to UCL in early 2019. The contents of the school are being discussed and efforts are being made to assure resources for involving early career scientists as well as stakeholders. The invitation for participation in the summer school will soon be announced widely to Papila partners and to a broader public.

CNRS worked also with the co-chairs of the GEIA (Global Emissions Initiative) and the colleagues at UCL, in order to organize the combined Papila summer school and the 2019 international conference of the GEIA project in Santiago, Chile. The fact that the PAPILA summer school will take place just before the GEIA symposium will help more early-stage researchers and more advanced scientists to participate to both GEIA and Papila summer school, and help them meet scientists from different regions of the world.

As part of WP6 activities, MPI-M has also developed the papilla website (<http://papila-h2020.eu>) as the central hub of information for PAPILA, on one hand to disseminate the project results and products, on the other hand to facilitate communication between the partners. All legal and monitoring documents are accessible for PAPILA community. MET Norway learned to use the TYPO3 content management system in order to assist the development and maintenance of the PAPILA website at MPI-M. Planning of the outreach events for potential users of PAPILA products started and will be further developed during upcoming secondments.

2. Corrective Measures

2.1 Please explain any delays accumulated in the secondments / activities / deliverables foreseen in the Grant Agreement and the measures taken to oversee them.

Some delays have occurred during the first year of the project and, for many of them, are due to funding issues for some partners. For example, UNAM (Mexico), USP (Brazil) and UPR (Puerto Rico) are not eligible for funding within Papila and were therefore not been able to send people for secondments on time according to the original plan. In order to overcome this problem, USP and UPR have submitted proposals to their local science foundations to ask for financial support. UNAM is trying to get involved in other projects that have similar objectives and funding to accomplish the planned tasks and possibly the secondments. The project management team keeps close contact with these partners and, if necessary, will define appropriate measures (e.g. postpone the secondments or redistribute tasks to other partners) is the partners still encounter funding issues. There were also some other delays accumulated due to time planning difficulties for some researchers. Some other secondments were shortened due to work, family or other personal reasons. In order to mitigate this issue,

an agreement is found with the concerned partners in order to postpone the secondments to appropriate time periods.

The few deliverables due during the first year concern for most of them the management aspects of the project (e.g. kick-off meeting, technical workshop, management plan, etc.). There were slight delays in some deliverables due mostly to impossibility of organising the related activities during the planned timeline (e.g. D1.2 on first technical workshop), lack of staff and time planning difficulties. However, all due reports have been delivered and the slight delays in the deliverables as well as in the secondments did not have impact on the planned tasks and on the overall success of the project as shown by the considerable progress accomplished in all WPs during this first year of the project.

2.2 Please indicate any potential risks identified and suggested approaches to mitigate them.

As explained in Section 2.1, one potential risk identified is unavailability of funding for some partners in South America, who do not receive funding within PAPILA (USP, UPR and UNAM), in order to accomplish their secondments. Some of these partners are still waiting for answers from their local funding agencies regarding their submitted proposals for financial support. As explained, appropriate measures will be taken by the management team in case of continuous financial difficulties for those partners, in order to make sure of no impact on the project objectives. So far such issues and related delays had no impact on the success of the project especially because the Papila products to be promoted are still under development and were not planned to be ready in 2018.

Some partners have pointed to the lack of published scientific findings specific to the South American region (mostly for agriculture but also for health, especially lack of local concentration response functions) which could have potential risks for some activities and products developed within Papila. The work is still in an early state and the research for region specific data continues. However, using in a first approach data from other regions (e.g. concentration-response functions developed for Europe, the US, or the globe) or more general methods (e.g. starting with a generic formulation for all crops instead of a species-specific formulation) may be considered. These are two possible solutions to mitigate the risk. The tools developed e.g. at INERIS on this “generic” basis could be adapted later as more specific scientific knowledge becomes available.

Another potential technical risk that has been identified by some partners is the large demand on storage capacity demanded by the project due to the multiple model simulations that are planned to be conducted at the computing facilities of the partners. In order to cope with the increasing demand, measures are being taken by each partner to increase the storage capacities associated to the project. Some partners (e.g. FMI, MET Norway, CNRS) have expertise in processing and archiving different type of datasets and agreed to support other teams in case of difficulties and agreed also to provide support and long-term storage of the Papila numerical datasets as indicated in the data management plan report (D5.1).

3. Ethical Issues

N/A

4. Progress in WP1 overall project management and coordination

A considerable scientific progress is accomplished by the Papila partners in both Europe and South America during the first year of the project. Several partners have indicated that the cooperation between the seconded researchers and the hosting partners was working smoothly and fruitfully. The management team at MPI-M and UCL has maintained good contact and communication with all partners through teleconferences, mailing lists and specific side meetings organized during international conferences and this allowed for the project to achieve its objectives for this first period. By summer 2019 around 28 person-month secondment will have taken place. Comparing to the planned activities for the first 18 months, the success rate of the implementation of the secondment is fairly low (around 22%). This was largely due to the administrative processes at the beginning of the project (i.e. financial transaction and remittance, employment status for Early Career Researchers). We hope to catch up on the plan in the second and third project year.